

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

“LIQUID PHASE SYNTHESIS OF COUMARINO BENZIMIDAZOLES FOR ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY”

Singh Mukesh*, Kurmi Mukesh

Birgunj Pratimachowk, Ward No-18, District:-Parsa, Zone:- Narayani (Nepal).

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 11/12/2017

Available online
30/09/2019

Keywords

Polymer,
Topoisomerase,
Oligosaccharide,
Oligonucleotide,
Neoplastic,
Antimicrobial.

ABSTRACT

The chemistry which is used to peptide synthesis that replaces insoluble cross-linked resins with soluble polymer supports in a strategy termed as liquid-phase organic synthesis (LPOS). This advance recent approach has been modified sufficiently that reagents and catalyst are now being bound to soluble polymer supports for use in solution-phase combinatorial synthesis. Several different types of polymers have been investigated as supports in LPOS and also incorporated for the synthesis of peptide oligosaccharide and oligonucleotide synthesis. The most commonly used soluble polymer support is polyethylene glycol (PEG). The wide acceptability of PEG is directly linked to its broad solubility profile: soluble in dimethylformamide, dichloromethane, toluene, acetonitrile, water, and methanol. Coumarino benzimidazole derivatives were found to possess various activities which includes anti bacterial, anti protozoal, antifungal, anti inflammatory, anti allergic agents, anthelmintic activity, anti-parasitic activity, cytotoxicity and DNA topoisomerase I inhibitors activity. Moreover many research groups have synthesized various benzimidazole compounds and tested for antiviral anti neoplastic and anti filarial agents. Based on these findings, we have synthesized various coumarino benzimidazole and screened for anti microbial activity. It was found that the derivatives S1, S2, S3 and S4 have shown significant antimicrobial activity against gram -ve bacteria with zone of inhibition high as compared to S5 - S8 and the derivatives S1-S8 do not show any significant activity against gram +ve organism which shown in table no.1.

Corresponding author

Singh Mukesh

Birgunj Pratimachowk, Ward No-18,
District:-Parsa, Zone:- Narayani(Nepal).
mukeshm.pharm@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **Singh Mukesh et al.** “Liquid Phase Synthesis of Coumarino Benzimidazoles for Antimicrobial Activity”. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2019;9(09).

Copy right © 2019 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

www.iajpr.com

INTRODUCTION

Chemistry on soluble polymer supports, termed as liquid-phase organic synthesis⁽¹⁾, is developing into an increasingly viable alternative or adjunct to the classical solid phase approach across the broad spectrum of polymer-supported organic chemistry. Recent advances in the field include the use of soluble polymers in the combinatorial synthesis of peptide and small-molecule libraries, as catalyst and reagent supports, and as functionalized polymer quench reagent for purifying solution-phase combinatorial libraries.

Facts and disadvantages of the solid-phase supports.

Synthesis on the solid-phase supports imposes a lot of limitations in the organic and combinatorial synthesis

- ❖ Inestimable values
- ❖ Lowered reactivities
- ❖ Extended reaction times
- ❖ Unequal distribution and access to the polymer-bound reaction site
- ❖ Fundamental problem of converting the solution-based reaction protocols to use under heterogeneous conditions

The chemistry which is used to peptide synthesis that replaces insoluble cross-linked resins with soluble polymer supports in a strategy termed as liquid-phase organic synthesis (LPOS). The fundamentals of this process involve chemistry being performed on a soluble-polymer-supported derivative with reagents in solution. After reaction completion, the polymer support is separated from the spent reagents by precipitation and is then collected by filtration. This approach has been modified sufficiently that reagents and catalyst are now being bound to soluble polymer supports for use in solution-phase combinatorial synthesis.

Several different types of polymers have been investigated as supports in LPOS and incorporation of soluble polymer into peptide oligosaccharide and oligonucleotide syntheses have appeared recently. The most commonly used soluble polymer support is polyethylene glycol (PEG). The wide acceptability of PEG is directly linked to its broad solubility profile: soluble in dimethylformamide, dichloromethane, toluene, acetonitrile, water, and methanol. It can be precipitated and recovered in 99% yield from solvents such as diethyl ether, isopropanol, cold ethanol.

To establish the structure of the drug molecule the new inventions in physico-chemical direction such as x-rays analysis, UV, IR, NMR, MASS are immensely helpful for medicinal chemist. In the biochemical view knowledge of drug-receptor interaction, pharmacokinetics, advances in enzymology, have immensely helped medicinal chemist in hypothesizing the correct mechanism of action of drug molecules.

Benzimidazole was fused form of benzene and imidazole. These are weakly basic as well as acidic having having MP 170 °C. Like imidazoles, they are attacked by benzoylchloride and caustic sodas to form dibenzoylated o-diamines. They are extremely stable to oxidizing and reducing agents⁽²⁾.

Coumarins are naturally occurring lactone which are fusion of pyrone ring with a benzene nucleus.

Aromatic nature of heterolytic ring of coumarin is disputable, because coumarin shows some reaction of aliphatic compounds and other characteristics of aromatic compounds⁽³⁾.

Antibiotics are microbial metabolites or their synthetic analogs produced by various species of micro-organism (bacteria, fungi, actinomycetes), which in small doses suppress the growth of other microorganisms and may eventually destroy them without serious toxicity to the host. However common usage often extends the term antibiotics to include synthetic antibacterial agents, such as sulfonamides and quinolones, which are not the product of microbes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SYNTHESIS

STEP 1: SYNTHESIS OF 6-BROMOCOUMARIN-3-CARBOXYLIC ACID

9.6 g of 5-bromo salicylaldehyde and 12.5 g of malonic acid; 0.3ml of aniline in 33ml of pyridine was heated with constant stirring for 2 hours at 60°C. Cool the reaction mixture and add 0.1N HCl. The precipitate form was collected by filtration and product was washed with water and methanol and dried. Resulting product was recrystallised from chloroform. A white solid for 6-bromo coumarin-3-carboxylic acid was obtained (66%)

Knoevenagel condensation

STEP 2: NITRATION OF 6-BROMOCOUMARIN-3-CARBOXYLIC ACID.

To the solution of 6-bromocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid (2mmol) in acetonitrile (10ml) was added CAN (2mmol) in acetonitrile (10ml) in three proportions over a period of 10-15 minutes with stirring. The reaction mixture was then stirred for specific time and then quenched by pouring over ice.

STEP 3: ATTACHMENT OF PEG-5000

1 mole of PEG-5000, 1.2 mole of 6-bromo-7-nitro coumarin-3-carboxylic acid, 1.2 mole of DCC and a pinch of DMAP is dissolved in DCM and stirred for 24 hours at room temperature.

STEP 4: AROMATIC NUCLEOPHILIC SUBSTITUTION REACTION (AMINATION)

Polymer bounded product was dissolved in DCM, 2 equiv of primary amine was added and stirred for a period of 12 hour.

STEP 5: REDUCTION REACTION

Above obtained aminated product was dissolved in 10 ml of methanol and then subjected to reduction by treating with 20 equiv. of Zn and 6 equiv. of ammonium chloride, stirred for 3 hours.

STEP 6: CYCLIZATION

Reduced product was cyclised to get benzimidazole ring by using trifluoro acetic acid (0.5 eq), 5 mL dichloromethane, and trimethylorthoformate (5 eq), and stir the reaction mixture at room temperature under nitrogen atmosphere.

STEP 7: POLYMER CLEAVAGE

3gm of polymer bounded coumarino benzimidazole was again dissolved in methanol and treated with 0.5gm of sodium methoxide was stirred for 10-12 hours to get polymer free coumarino benzimidazole derivatives of various primary amines.

IDENTIFICATION AND CHARACTERISATION

The compounds synthesized were identified and characterized by following methods such as:

- Melting point determination
- Thin layer chromatography
- Infrared spectroscopy
- Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy
- Mass spectroscopy

Melting point determination:

The melting point is a valuable criterion for the purity of an organic compound because of of pure crystalline compound has a definite and sharp melting point. The melting points of the synthesized pure compounds were carried out using Thiel's tube method ⁽⁴⁾.

Thin layer chromatography:

TLC is a method of analysis in which the stationary phase is a finely subdivided solid which is spread over as a thin layer on a rigid plate and mobile phase, a liquid, allowed to migrate across the surface of the plate. The technique is widely used for the identification of the organic compounds with characteristic R_f values. This method is also applied to determine the progress of the reaction and to examine the purity of the end product ⁽⁵⁾. Pre-coated silica plates were used and Hexane: Ethyl acetate in the ratio of 2:2 was used as a mobile phase. After the development of the chromatogram the spots were detected by placing the plate in UV chamber.

Infrared spectroscopy:

IR spectroscopy is one of the most important tools for determining the various functional groups and the possible chemical structure. The important advantage of IR over the other technique is that it gives fingerprints ($1300-650\text{cm}^{-1}$) information about the structure (functional group, bonding with each other) of molecules easily. No two compounds have identical fingerprint region. This technique is based upon the molecular vibration of the compound such that each and every bond will vibrate at the different frequencies and this vibration frequency corresponds to the IR frequency. Thus IR spectra of each and every bond will be formed ^(6,7). The IR spectrum was recorded in SHIMADZU FTIR 8400S SPECTROMETER.

Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy:

The interaction between matter and electromagnetic forces can be observed by subjecting a substance simultaneously to two magnetic forces, one stationary and other varying at some radio frequency. At a particular combination of fields, energy is absorbed by the sample and absorption can be observed as a change in signal developed by a radio frequency detector and amplifier. This energy of absorption can be related to a magnetic dipolar nature of the spinning nuclei. This technique is useful in assuming the structure of the molecule ^(8, 9). The NMR spectra of the compounds were carried out in Bruker spectrosprin-400 NMR spectrophotometer. The solvent used was chloroform.

Mass spectroscopy:

This technique is useful in providing information regarding the atomic and molecular weights, structure, mechanism, kinetics of the reaction and mixture analysis. The technique involves bombardment of electrons and converted to highly energetic positively charged ions (molecular ions), which can break up into smaller ions (fragment ions) and sorting them in gas phase, into a spectrum according to their mass/charge ratio ⁽¹⁰⁾. The Mass spectra of the compounds were carried out in Electron spray mass spectrometer.

VARIOUS COUMARINO BENZIMIDAZOLE COMPOUNDS

COMPOUND CODE: S 1

1. Molecular formula : $C_{18}H_{12}N_2O_4$
2. Molecular weight : 320.98
3. Chemical name : methyl 6-oxo-1-phenyl-1,6-dihydrochromeno[6,7-d]imidazole-7-carboxylate
4. Molecular composition : C (67.50%) H (3.78%) N (8.75%) O (19.98%)
5. Melting point : $260^{\circ}C$
6. Colour : White
7. State : Solid
8. Solubility : Chloroform and Water
9. Rf value : 0.54
10. Percentage yield : 98%
11. IR spectral data : C=O (1686.70), C-O-C (1171.23), C-N (1251.93), C-H Ali (2939.01), C-H Ar(2941.81), C-C (951.93), C=C (1567.95), C=N (2237.42)
12. NMR spectral data : 6.473-6.452 δ (d, ArH, 2H), 7.153 δ (s, ArH, 1H) 7.147-7.010 δ (d, ArH, 5H), 2.874 δ (s, AliH, 3H), 8.400 δ (s, ArH, 1H)

IR Spectra of methyl 6-oxo-1-phenyl-1,6-dihydrochromeno[6,7-d]imidazole-7-carboxylate

IR spectral Data : C=O (1686.70), C-O-C (1171.23), C-N (1251.93), C-H Ali (2939.01), C-H Ar (2941.81), C-C (951.93), C=C (1567.95), C=N (2237.42).

NMR Spectra of methyl-(2-methylphenyl)-6-oxo-1,6-dihydrochromeno[6,7-d]imidazole-7-carboxylate.

NMR spectral Data : 2.495δ(s, AliH, 3H), 6.914-6.618δ (d, ArH, 4H) 8.503δ(s, ArH, 1H), 7.505δ(s, ArH, 1H), 1.193δ(s, AliH, 3H), 7.330-7.328δ (d, ArH, 2H),

COMPOUND CODE: S 3.

1. Molecular formula : C₁₉H₁₄N₂O₄
2. Molecular weight : 334.32
3. Chemical name : methyl-(3-methylphenyl)-6-oxo-1,6-dihydrochromeno[6,7-d]imidazole-7-carboxylate
4. Molecular composition : C(68.26%) H (4.22%) N (8.38%) O (19.14%)
5. Melting point : 240°C
6. Colour : yellowish white
7. State : Solid
8. Solubility : Chloroform and water
9. R_f value : 0.61
10. Percentage yield : 95%
11. IR spectral data : C=O (1750.2), C-O-C (1110.9), C-N (1280.6), C-H Ali (2738.7), C-H Ar (2889.2), C-C (1060.8), C=C (1639.4), C=N (2164.0)
12. NMR spectral data : 2.212δ(s, AliH, 3H), 3.626δ(s, AliH, 3H), 8.189δ(s, ArH, 1H), 7.721δ (d, ArH, 1H) 7.310δ (d, ArH, 2H), 7.000-6.675δ (d, ArH, 4H)

IR Spectra of methyl-(3-methylphenyl)-6-oxo-1,6-dihydrochromeno[6,7-d]imidazole-7-carboxylate.

IR spectral Data : C=O (1750.2), C-O-C (1110.9), C-N (1280.6), C-H Ali (2738.7), C-H Ar (2889.2), C-C (1060.8), C=C (1639.4), C=N (2164.0)

NMR Spectra of methyl-(3-methylphenyl)-6-oxo-1,6-dihydrochromeno [6,7-d] imidazole-7-carboxylate.

IR Spectra of methyl-(4-methylphenyl)-6-oxo-1,6-dihydrochromeno[6,7-d]imidazole-7-carboxylate.

IR spectral data : C=O (1762.62), C-O-C (1166.85), C-N (1230.38), C-H Ali (2962.85), C-H Ar (3184.62), C-C (985.85) C=C (1571.88), C=N (1903.47).

NMR Spectra of methyl-(4-methylphenyl)-6-oxo-1,6-dihydrochromeno[6,7-d]imidazole-7-carboxylate.

NMR spectral Data : 2.362 δ (s, AliH, 3H), 3.627 δ (s, AliH, 3H) 8.178 δ (s, ArH, 1H), 7.735 δ (d, ArH, 1H) 7.574 δ (d, ArH, 2H), 7.000-6.766 δ (d, ArH, 4H).

COMPOUND CODE: S 5

1. Molecular formula : C₁₈H₁₁N₃O₆
2. Molecular weight : 365.29
3. Chemical name : methyl 1-(3-nitrophenyl)-6-oxo-1,6-dihydrochromeno[6,7-d]imidazole-7-carboxylate
4. Molecular composition : C (59.18%) H (3.04%) N (11.50%) O (26.28%)
5. Melting point : 270-273^oC
6. Colour : Slight Brown
7. State : Solid
8. Solubility : Chloroform and Water
9. Rf value : 0.93
10. Percentage yield : 94%
11. IR spectral data : NO₂(1396.4),C=O (1769.4),C-O-C (1099.3) C-N (1296.1),C-H Ali (2769.5),C-H Ar(2935.5),C-C (948.9), C=C (1635.5), C=N (2133.1)
12. NMR spectral data : 3.643 δ (s,AliH,3H), 8.153 δ (d,ArH,1H), 8.565 δ (s,ArH,1H), 8.325 δ (s,ArH,1H), 7.997 δ (d,ArH,1H), 8.283 δ (d,ArH,1H), 8.284 δ (d,ArH,1H), 7.392-7.282 δ (d,ArH,2H)

IR spectra of methyl-(3-nitrophenyl)-6-oxo-1,6-dihydrochromeno[6,7-d]imidazole-7-carboxylate.

IR spectral data : NO₂ (1396.4), C=O (1769.4), C-O-C (1099.3) C-N (1296.1), C-H Ali (2769.5), C-H Ar (2935.5), C-C (948.9), C=C (1635.5), C=N (2133.1).

NMR spectra of methyl-(3-nitrophenyl)-6-oxo-1, 6-dihydrochromeno [6, 7-d] imidazole-7-carboxylate.

NMR spectral data : 3.643 δ (s,AlH,3H), 8.153 δ (d,ArH,1H), 8.565 δ (s,ArH,1H), 8.325 δ (s,ArH,1H), 7.997 δ (d,ArH,1H), 8.283 δ (d,ArH,1H), 8.284 δ (d,ArH,1H), 7.392-7.282 δ (d,ArH,2H).

COMPOUND CODE: S6.

1. Molecular formula : C₁₈H₁₁N₃O₆
2. Molecular weight : 365.29
3. Chemical name : methyl 1-(4-nitrophenyl)-6-oxo-1,6-dihydrochromeno[6,7-d]imidazole-7-carboxylate
4. Molecular composition : C (59.18%) H (3.04%) N (11.50%) O (26.28%)
5. Melting point : 276^oC
6. Colour : Slight Brown
7. State : Solid
8. Solubility : Chloroform and Water
9. Rf value : 0.76
10. Percentage yield : 92%
11. IR spectral data : NO₂ (1351.78),C=O (1750.74),C-O-C (1102.74) N(1286.68),C-H Ali (2738.68), C-H Ar (2912.36), C-C (951.69), C=C (1645.55), C=N (2087.89)
12. NMR spectral data : 3.498 δ (s, AliH, 3H), 8.657 δ (s, ArH, 1H) 8.117 δ (d, ArH, 1H), 7.859 δ (d, ArH, 1H),7.659 δ (d, ArH, 1H), 7.239-7.052 δ (d, ArH, 4H)

IR Spectra of : methyl 1-(4-nitrophenyl)-6-oxo-1,6-dihydrochromeno[6,7-d]imidazole-7-carboxylate.

IR spectral data : NO₂ (1351.78), C=O (1750.74), C-O-C (1102.74) C-N (1286.68), C-H Ali (2738.68), C-H Ar (2912.36), C-C (951.69), C=C (1645.55), C=N (2087.89).

NMR Spectra of : methyl 1-(4-nitrophenyl)-6-oxo-1,6-dihydrochromeno[6,7-d]imidazole-7-carboxylate.

NMR spectral data : 3.498 δ (s, AliH, 3H), 8.657 δ (s, ArH, 1H) 8.117 δ (d, ArH, 1H), 7.859 δ (d, ArH, 1H), 7.659 δ (d, ArH, 1H), 7.239-7.052 δ (d, ArH, 4H).

COMPOUND CODE: S7.

1. Molecular formula : $C_{13}H_{10}N_2O_4$
2. Molecular weight : 258.22
3. Chemical name : methyl 1-methyl-6-oxo-1,6-dihydrochromeno[6,7- d]imidazole-7-carboxylate
4. Molecular composition : C (60.47%) H (3.90%) N (10.85%) O (24.78%)
5. Melting point : 245 $^{\circ}$ C
6. Colour : White
7. State : Solid
8. Solubility : Chloroform and Water
9. Rf value : 0.36
10. Percentage yield : 93%
11. IR spectral data : C=O (1697.12), C-O-C (1098.11), C-N (1352.81), C-H Ali (2958.06), C-H Ar (3255.02), C-C (952.83), C=C (1468.49), C=N (2094.97)
12. NMR spectral data : 8.184 δ (s, ArH, 1H), 8.153 δ (d, ArH, 1H) 7.654 δ (d, ArH, 1H), 7.493 δ (d, ArH, 1H) 2.182 δ (s, AliH, 3H), 3.307 δ (s, AliH, 3H)

IR Spectra of : methyl 1-methyl-6-oxo-1,6-dihydrochromeno[6,7-d]imidazol carboxylate.

IR spectral data : C=O (1697.12), C-O-C (1098.11), C-N (1352.81), C-H Ali (2958.06), C-H Ar (3255.02), C-C (952.83) C=C (1468.49), C=N (2094.97).

NMR Spectra of : methyl 1-methyl-6-oxo-1,6-dihydrochromeno[6,7-d]imidazol carboxylate.

NMR spectral data : 8.184 δ (s, ArH, 1H), 8.153 δ (d, ArH, 1H) 7.654 δ (d, ArH, 1H), 7.493 δ (d, ArH, 1H) 2.182 δ (s, AliH, 3H), 3.307 δ (s, AliH, 3H)

NMR Spectra of : methyl 1-ethyl-6-oxo-1,6-dihydrochromenof[6,7-d]imidazol carboxylate.

NMR spectral data: 8.319δ (d, ArH, 1H), 8.199δ (d, ArH, 1H) 3.914δ(s, AliH, 3H), 7.369-7.249δ (d, ArH, 2H), 2.415δ (t, AliH, 3H), 3.866δ (quat, AliH, 2H).

ANTIMICROBIOLOGICAL SCREENING INTRODUCTION ^(11, 12, 13)

The determination of anti microbial activity which is followed here is a relative method and not absolute. Responses of an organism to an unknown compound are compared with responses to the standard preparation of known composition and concentration. This determination indicates whether the organism is "Sensitive" or "Resistant" to the agent. The organism being 'sensitive' means that the antimicrobial agent at clinically attainable concentration inhibits the organism, 'resistant' means that the growth of the organism is not inhibited.

Anti microbial evaluation can be done by two methods. They are:

- Tube Dilution Method or Turbidimetric Method
- Agar Diffusion Method or Cup Plate Method

Tube Dilution Method

The dilutions of the anti-microbial agents are prepared in nutrient medium such that the concentration of the drug covers its clinical significant range. An equal volume of broth containing 10⁵ to 10⁶ bacteria per ml is added to each tube and to a control tube that contains no anti-microbial agent. The tubes are examined for visible turbidity after overnight incubation. This method is used for determining anti-microbial susceptibility in liquid media; however it is cumbersome and has given way in the clinical laboratory to micro-dilution tests and automated testing procedures. This method is used to determine the minimum inhibitory concentration of an anti-microbial agent.

Requirement:

Test tubes, antibiotics, microbial culture, spectrophotometer, laminar airflow, Inoculating loop, Bunsen burner.

Procedure:

1. Five different concentration of the standard were prepared for preparing the standard drug by diluting the stock solution of the standard solution of antibiotics.
2. Medium concentration was selected and solution of antibiotics (unknown) was diluted.
3. 1ml of each concentration of standard solution and 1ml of sample solution was placed in separate tubes.
4. In each tube 9ml of nutrient media previously inoculated by test organism was added.
5. At the same time two control tubes were prepared.
 - One containing the inoculated culture media.
 - Inoculated culture media and 0.5ml of diluted formaldehyde solution. (Blank).
6. All tubes were placed at the specific temperature for 3-4hrs.
7. After inoculation 0.5ml of diluted formaldehyde solution was added to each tube.
8. The growth of test organism was measured by determination of extinction at 530nm of each of the solution in the tube against the blank

Agar Diffusion Method

In this technique various agar plates are prepared by pouring nutrient agar media, each of them is inoculated with a particular microorganism, like gram +ve and gram -ve bacteria. Example: Staphylococcus aureus, Pseudomonas aureginosa, Escherichia coli, Salmonella typhi, bacillus substillus etc.

After agar solidifies, cups are made in nutrient agar. The anti microbial test drug are placed in the cups. The drug diffuses through the agar around the cup. The plates are incubated at a temperature of 37⁰C for 24hrs for bacteria and 28⁰C for 48hrs for fungi. The anti microbial substance inhibits the growth if microorganism and produces a clear zone of inhibition. The diameter of this zone can be measured and is a measure of the degree of activity of the anti microbial substances.

Requirement:

Microbial inoculums, culture media, petri dish, measuring cylinder, needle, inoculating tube, forceps, incubator, and aseptic area.

Sample Solution

The solution of the various derivatives in concentration of 20µgm was prepared. The solvent used for dilution was distilled water similar to standard dilution.

Procedure:

1. Microbial inoculum with the required quantity or suspension or test organism was prepared.
2. The prepared microbial suspension was added in the media and mixed with and transferred into petri dish.
3. Ciprofloxacin 30µg/ml in water was prepared as standard.
4. The solution was applied to the surface of the solid media in sterile cylinder or in cavities prepared in agar plate.
5. For each unknown sample, prepared a set of three plates (18 cylinder or cavities) and filled alternatively with the standard solution.
6. Incubated the plate for 18-48 hrs at the specified temperature and measured the diameters of the zone of inhibition.

Observation:

Observe the zone around the hole by antibiotics zone reader or visually.

Calculation:

The percentage of inhibition was calculated by the formula:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{\text{Diameter of the inhibition zone}}{\text{Diameter of the petri plate}} \times 100$$

Precautions:

- The uniform volume of the solution must be added to each cylinder or cavity sufficient to fill the cavity or holes.
- When paper disc are used, it should be sterilized on both the sides, if sterilized by UV radiation.
- Add test solution and standard solution in the alternate manner around the dish.
- Remaining microbial culture is to be discarded after adding disinfectant.
- Cavities in the agar plate should be uniform. Remove the whole material and empty it completely.
- Do not fill excess amount of solution in the cylinder or cavity.
- In place of cavities, dish system is more is more easy and convenient for the laboratory use.
- One level assay with standard curve.
- Dissolve an accurate quantity of the standard preparation of the antibiotic in suitable solvent. This stock solution should be stored in refrigerator and used within the period as specified in the pharmacopoeia⁽¹⁴⁾.

Procedures for the screening of antibacterial activity

1 litre of nutrient agar medium was prepared by dissolving ingredients in 1 litre of distilled water, the pH of the medium was adjusted to 6.5-6.6 using buffer and the media so prepared was sterilized by autoclaving at a temperature of 121⁰C for 15 min. Sterilization of equipments required.

Petridishes, glass syringes, cork borer and test tubes were sterilized by dry heat sterilization at 160⁰C for 1 hour in a hot air oven.

Preparation of Agar plates

The media was cooled at 45-48⁰C and inoculated with test 10⁵ or 10⁶ cells / ml suspension of organisms. It was mixed well and 30ml of inoculated media was transferred into each of the plate (for each organism) and was kept at room temperature until the agar medium was completely solidified. Four cups were made per plate using a cork borer. A sterile atmosphere was being maintained during the entire process by carrying out the work under laminar flow bench. 0.01 ml solution of test drug, 0.1 ml of the standard and control solutions were added to the cups in the petri dishes. The petri dishes were kept for 2hrs to allow the drug to diffuse into the agar media. All plates were incubated for 24hrs at 37⁰C at the end of the incubation period, diameter of the zones of inhibition were measured and recorded^(15,16).

Antibacterial sensitivity test

All synthesized compounds were screened for anti microbial activity against following bacteria:

Gram (-)ve bacteria:

Echerichia coli ATCC25922

Gram (+)ve bacteria:

Staphylococcus aureus ATCC 25923

Table1. Showing zone of inhibition of different derivatives on bacteria.

COMPOUND CODE	E.COLI	STAPH.AUREUS
S1	2.18±0.01 ***	0.80±0.02 ns
S2	1.73±0.12 ***	0.80±0.06 ns
S3	1.70±0.05 ***	0.88±0.01 ns
S4	1.46±0.14 *	0.82±0.02 ns
S5	0.75±0.02 ns	0.73±0.11 ns
S6	0.95±0.02 ns	0.82±0.06 ns
S7	0.91±0.02 ns	0.82±0.02 ns
S8	1.19±0.15 ns	0.87±0.01 ns
CONTROL	0.98±0.07	0.95±0.04
STANDARD(CIPROFLOXACIN)	3.85±0.05 ***	3.60±0.03 ***

Zone of inhibition (in cm)

***-P<0.001

*-P<0.05

Derivatives 1-4 show significant activity against gram -ve organism and 5-8 are inactive. Derivatives 1-8 do not show activity against gram +ve organism

DATA OF VARIOUS DERIVATIVES

Compound code	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	MP °C	Yield (%)	Rf	Antimicrobial activity	
						Gram - ve	Gram + ve
S1	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄	320.98	260°C	98%	0.54	Significant	Not active
S2	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	334.32	255°C	93%	0.77	Significant	Not active
S3	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	334.32	240°C	95%	0.61	Significant	Not active
S4	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	334.32	233°C	95%	0.88	Significant	Not active
S5	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₆	365.29	273°C	94%	0.93	Not active	Not active
S6	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₆	365.29	276°C	92%	0.76	Not active	Not active
S7	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄	258.22	245°C	93%	0.36	Not active	Not active
S8	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄	258.22	270°C	93%	0.54	Not active	Not active

Among all the synthesized derivatives S1, S2, S3, S4 derivatives had shown the significant anti-microbial activities at 20mcg/ml.

DISCUSSION

Different coumarino benzimidazole derivatives were synthesized by liquid phase method where PEG-5000 is used as a supporting polymer and bounded to the previously prepared 6-bromo7-nitro coumarin-3-carboxylic acid using DCC and DMAP. The product obtained was treated with various primary amines like aniline, o-toluidine, m-toluidine, p-toluidine, 3-nitro aniline, 4-nitro aniline, methyl amine and ethyl amine.

The compounds synthesized were identified and characterized by the following methods:

- Melting point determination: The melting point of the synthesized compound was determined by Thief's melting point tube. (Capillary tube method)
- Thin layer chromatography: the solvent used was Ethyl acetate: n-Hexane:
- IR spectroscopy: The IR spectral analysis was carried out using KBr pellets.
- NMR spectroscopy: The NMR spectrum analysis was carried out in 400 spectrospin NMR at Indian Institute Of Science, Bangalore. The solvent used was CDCl₃ and D₂O
- MASS spectroscopy: The Mass spectroscopy was carried out in High Resolution Mass Spectroscopy at Indian Institute Of Science, Bangalore.

A total of 8 derivatives were synthesized. All the compounds were screened for their anti-microbial activity using cup-plate method (ciprofloxacin as a standard) and all the synthesized compounds were found to be active against E.coli and inactive against staph.aureus.

STRUCTURE OF VARIOUS COUMARINO BENZIMIDAZOLE DERIVATIVES HAVING SIGNIFICANT ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY

S8

DATA OF VARIOUS DERIVATIVES

Compound code	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	MP °C	Yield (%)	Rf	Antimicrobial activity	
						Gram - ve	Gram + ve
S1	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄	320.98	260°C	98%	0.54	Significant	Not active
S2	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	334.32	255°C	93%	0.77	Significant	Not active
S3	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	334.32	240°C	95%	0.61	Significant	Not active
S4	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	334.32	233°C	95%	0.88	Significant	Not active
S5	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₆	365.29	273°C	94%	0.93	Not active	Not active
S6	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₆	365.29	276°C	92%	0.76	Not active	Not active
S7	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄	258.22	245°C	93%	0.36	Not active	Not active
S8	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄	258.22	270°C	93%	0.54	Not active	Not active

Among all the synthesized derivatives S1, S2, S3, S4 derivatives shown the significant anti-microbial activities at 20mcg/ml.

RESULT AND CONCLUSION

A total of 8 derivatives were synthesized. All the compounds were screened for anti microbial activity using cup plate method, using ciprofloxacin as standard. The derivatives S1, S2, S3, S4 derivatives shown the significant anti-microbial activities at 20mcg/ml.

SUMMARY

The whole project work can be summarized as follows;

1. Liquid phase synthesis of Coumarino Benzimidazole were carried out and screened for antimicrobial activities.
2. Synthesis of 6-bromocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid was carried out by reaction with 5-bromo salicylaldehyde and malonic acid, aniline in pyridine was heated with constant stirring for 2 hours at 60°C.
3. 6-bromocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid was nitrated with ceric ammonium nitrate using the solvent acetonitrile with constant stirring.
4. PEG-5000 was used as a supporting polymer which was bounded with 6-bromo7-nitro coumarin-3-carboxylic acid by stirring at room temperature.
5. Polymer bounded compound was treated with various primary amines like aniline, methylamine, ethylamine, o-toluidine, m-toluidine, p-toluidine, 3-nitroaniline, 4-nitroaniline. To get various derivatives.
6. Amine substituted product was reduced by treating with zinc and ammonium chloride.
7. Reduced product was cyclised to get benzimidazole ring by using trifluoro acetic acid and trimethylorthoformate.
8. Polymer support was cleaved by treating with sodium methoxide to get various coumarino benzimidazole derivatives.
9. DCM was used as a solvent and diethyl ether as a precipitating solvent.
10. The various synthesized derivatives were screened for their antimicrobial activities. The antimicrobial activity was performed on E.coli and S. aureus using ciprofloxacin and as a standard by using cup plate method.

DATA OF VARIOUS DERIVATIVES

Compound code	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	MP °C	Yield (%)	Rf	Antimicrobial activity	
						Gram - ve	Gram + ve
S1	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄	320.98	260°C	98%	0.54	Significant	Not active
S2	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	334.32	255°C	93%	0.77	Significant	Not active
S3	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	334.32	240°C	95%	0.61	Significant	Not active
S4	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	334.32	233°C	95%	0.88	Significant	Not active
S5	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₆	365.29	273°C	94%	0.93	Not active	Not active
S6	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₆	365.29	276°C	92%	0.76	Not active	Not active
S7	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄	258.22	245°C	93%	0.36	Not active	Not active
S8	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄	258.22	270°C	93%	0.54	Not active	Not active

The compounds synthesized were identified and characterized by following methods, such as:

1. Melting point determination – the MP of organic compounds were determined by Thiel's melting point tube.
2. TLC – the solvent used was ethyl acetate and n-hexane.
3. IR spectroscopy – it was carried out using KBr pellets.
4. NMR spectroscopy – NMR spectra of the compounds was carried out at IISc, the solvent used was chloroform and water.

STRUCTURE OF VARIOUS COUMARINO BENZIMIDAZOLE DERIVATIVES HAVING SIGNIFICANT ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY

S8

REFERENCES

1. Wentworth PJr. Recent developments and applications of liquid-phase strategies in organic synthesis. Trends in Biotech 1999;11:448-452.
2. Ming G S, Chun C. Ytterbium Perfluorooctanesulfonates Catalyzed Synthesis of Benzimidazole Derivatives In Fluorous Solvents. J of Fluorine Chem 2007Jan; 128: 232–235.
3. Ramani A, Chanda B M et al. One Pot Synthesis of Coumarin. Green Chemistry.1999 June;13:163-165.
4. Ibrahim M E D, El-Sayed I A W, Ahmed G E M et al. Synthesis of 3-Pyrimidyl- and 3-Pyranlyl-5, 6-benzocoumarin Derivatives. Bull Korean Chem Soc. 2002; (23) 4:610-612.
5. Christie R M, Lui C H. Studies of Fluorescent Dyes: Part 2. An Investigation of the Synthesis and Electronic Spectral Properties of Substituted 3-(20-Benzimidazolyl) Coumarins. Dyes and Pigments. 2000 March; 47(1-2): 79-89.
6. Brain, Furniss, Anthony J, Hanna F. Determination of Physical constants; Determination of melting points. Vogel's Text Book Practical Organic Chemistry London: Longman Singapore Publishers; 1989: 236-8.
7. Stahl E, Ashworth M R F. Thin Layer Chromatography. A Laboratory Handbook. Springer Verlag 2nd ed. Berlin, Heidelberg, Newyork; 1996: 6-29.
8. Silverstein R M, Bassler C G, Morrill T C. Infra red spectrometry. Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compound 5th Ed.New York: John Wiley & Sons Inc; 1991: 100-30.
9. Williams Kemp. Infrared Spectroscopy. Organic spectroscopy. New York: Macmillan Publishing Co., Inc.; 1991: 56-86.
10. Silverstein R M, Bassler C G, Morrill T C. Ultraviolet spectrometry. Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compound 5th Ed.New York: John Wiley & Sons; 1991: 289 300.
11. Sharma B K. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy. Spectroscopy 11th Ed. India: Goel Publishing House; 1995-96: 484-5.
12. Williams Kemp. Mass Spectroscopy. Organic spectroscopy. New York: Macmillan Publishing Co., Inc.; 1991: 56-86.
13. Principle and practice of drug stability by Jen carstensen. 2nd edition. Published by Marcel Dekker.
14. I R S Gaud, Gupta. Microbial Assay in Practical Microbiology, 1st Edition; 199-1166.
15. Collee F G, Marr W. Specimen collection, culture, containers and media chapter 5 in Mackies and McCartney practical Medical Microbiology, J G College, A G Fraser, B P Marmion and A Simmons, Newyork. Church Hill, Livingstone, 1996: 105-7.
16. Indian Pharmacopoeia, 1996, A-100-A110.

54878478451171211

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **ScopeMed** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

